

AN INNOVATIVE METHOD OF TEACHING THE FUNDAMENTALS OF THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

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Аннотация

В данной статье представлен обзор существующих виртуальных тренажёров и их применения в нефтегазовой отрасли. Раскрыта сущность имитационного метода обучения в качестве эффективного способа преподавания технических дисциплин. Для проведения занятий используется имитационный программный продукт AnyLogic.

Abstract

This article provides an overview of existing virtual simulators and their application in the oil and gas industry. The essence of the simulation method of teaching as an effective way of teaching technical disciplines is revealed. The AnyLogic simulation software product is used to conduct classes.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada virtual trenajorlar va ularning neft va gaz sanoatida qo'llanilishi haqida umumiy ma'lumot berilgan. Texnika fanlarni o'qitishning samarali usuli sifatida o'qitishning imitatsiya usulining mohiyati ochib berilgan. Darslarni o'tkazish uchun AnyLogic imitatsion dasturi mahsulotidan foydalaniladi.

Ключевые слова: виртуальный тренажер, модель, обучение, имитационный метод, технология.

Key words: virtual simulator, model, training, simulation method, technology.

Kalit so'zlar: virtual trenajor, model, o'qitish, imitatsiya usuli, texnologiya.

In today's technologically advanced world, it is impossible to compete in production without the use of digital innovations. As for all industrialized countries, this issue is also of particular importance for our country. The rational use of advanced technologies contributes to the productivity of enterprises, thereby providing a real opportunity to jump over a number of stages of development and introduce modern solutions that are just beginning to be used in progressive industrial countries.

The rational use of virtual simulators in the educational process not only improves working skills, but also creates a safe and environmentally friendly environment, and also saves impressive financial resources.

According to a report by Aberdeen Research Group, the average cost of equipment shutdown in any manufacturing sector today is between \$30,000 and \$50,000 per hour. Productivity losses in petrochemical production are 2-5%. Regardless of industry sector, such incidents occur on average 3.6 times per year and last three to four hours. For the average company, this means a loss of at least \$500,000 per year.

Implementing practical training programs in specific industries can be quite challenging. This is especially true for the oil and gas industry.

Problems of computer simulation simulators and the development of their software are presented in the works. Dzortseva V.M. [2], Lutsenko E.V. [3], Kazaka A.B. [4], Viger I.N. [5],

Narayanan P.J., Render R.W., Flyson D.I. There are such software for simulation modeling: Aimsun, AnyLogic, AweSim, Deneb/Quest, Enterprise Dynamics, etc.

Interest in such modeling tools continues to grow as computer performance increases. Proceedings of international conferences in the field of modern modeling and simulation tools, for example, International Training and Education Conference (ITEC), International Society for Modeling and Simulation (SCS), Special Interest Group on Graphics and Interactive Technologies (Interactive Technologies (SigGraph), International Conference on artificial reality and “teleexistence.” According to the International Conference on Artificial Reality and Teleexistence, computer modeling is increasingly used in aviation, navigation, energy, military, medical and space technology, as well as in those areas where conducting physical experiments is difficult or restrictive. regulated by law (models).

Simulation modeling methods are currently well developed in domestic science and allow us to assess the potential for future development of traffic intensity at a qualitatively new level under various options for the development of mixed traffic. As a result, today they are also used to study large-scale oil and gas projects.

In our case, the term “simulation modeling” has a broader meaning, not limiting it to technical products based on virtual reality. In our opinion, simulation modeling is immersion in a situation as close as possible to a professional environment in order to analyze a situation unfolding over time or solve a real professional problem. Thus, the simulation method is integrated into all the main didactic concepts, such as the competency-based approach, practice-oriented learning, contextual approach to learning, interactive learning and case method. To create an accurate computer model, we will use the AnyLogic program, which does not require any costs and is available to all users.

Anylogic is an excellent example of a unique simulation modeling tool - a software product that allows you to develop models based on all currently known approaches, including process (discrete-event), system dynamic and agent-based modeling.

With the simulation method of teaching, didactic forms, methods and means are combined to model the subject-technical and socio-communicative content of a specialist’s future professional activity [6]; as N.Ya rightly notes. Seygushev and others, “such training is a sign system that imposes abstract knowledge about them on the outline of professional activity” [7c].

In this teaching method, as in the traditional one, educational materials are, firstly, presented in the form of educational texts, educational video and audio materials, which provide a theoretical basis for assimilation. Secondly, the theoretical knowledge base is implemented using new forms and methods of simulation modeling in the subject, technical and social content of future professional activities. Thus, there is a transition from the student’s basic knowledge to more realistic models that reproduce fragments of real professional situations and activities.

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